

“Smart Wireless Water Meter with Web DB using Internet of Things”

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Abstract— Water conservation is a critical global issue, particularly in urban and rural areas facing diminishing supplies. In many residential and industrial settings, shared water meters lead to unaccounted consumption and excessive use. This project presents a Smart Wireless Water Meter leveraging IoT technology to monitor and manage water usage efficiently. The system employs an ATMEGA328P microcontroller for data acquisition, ESP8266 for communication, and LoRa SX1278 modules for wireless data transmission. Real-time water flow and level data are processed, displayed on an OLED screen, and used to automate motor control via a relay. A cloud-based web database enables remote access to consumption analytics and alerts. This IoT-driven solution enhances water conservation efforts by providing real-time insights, improving resource management, and supporting automated control in residential, industrial, and agricultural applications.

Keywords - *IoT, Water Conservation, Real Time Monitoring, Smart Wireless Water Meter, Sustainable Water Management, Cloud-based Database, Automated Alert.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Water is one of the most vital resources for sustaining life, yet it is increasingly scarce due to population growth, urbanization, and climate change. Efficient water management is now a necessity rather than a choice. Traditional water meters often fail to provide accurate, real-time data, making it difficult to track and control water usage effectively. The problem is even more pronounced in shared residential complexes and industries, where a common water meter results in aggregated billing and disputes over individual consumption.

To overcome these challenges, we propose the "Smart Wireless Water Meter with Web Database Using IoT," an advanced system designed to monitor and manage water consumption efficiently. This system employs IoT-based technology to provide real-time tracking of water usage at household, industrial, and municipal levels.

The system uses advanced flow and level sensors to ensure precise data collection. This data is then wirelessly transmitted using LoRa technology to a central receiver, where it is processed and uploaded to a cloud-based web database. Users can access their water consumption insights, alerts, and analytics via web and mobile interfaces, helping them adopt sustainable usage habits and reduce billing

disputes. Beyond individual users, municipal water authorities and industries can benefit from this system. Real-time data enables them to optimize water distribution, detect leakages, and minimize waste. The integration of automated control mechanisms, such as motorized valves and relays, further enhances operational efficiency. A key feature of this system is its machine learning integration, which analyses usage patterns, detects leaks, and predicts excessive consumption. This predictive intelligence enhances proactive maintenance and reduces water wastage. Additionally, the system's serverless architecture allows scalability, making it cost-effective for large-scale deployment across residential, commercial, and industrial settings.

The environmental impact of this system is significant, as it encourages responsible water consumption and reduces waste. By combining IoT, cloud computing, and data analytics, the system ensures efficient resource management, contributing to global water conservation efforts.

II. RELATED WORK

Smart wireless water meters integrated with IoT have been extensively explored to optimize water usage and enable efficient real-time monitoring and management. A vast number of studies and ideas have been explored by different researchers in which they have integrated with IoT, wireless sensor networks (WSN), and automated control mechanisms for efficient water management. Carlos and Fernando [1] It presents various applications, including real-time monitoring of water consumption, demand forecasting, and user engagement through smart meters and communication systems the ability of SWMS to monitor the state of water resources and improve overall management by providing accurate data and insights. Chandraman M and Sunandha B [2] In this system uses real-time flow data from sensors and transmits it to a cloud database, where it is stored for future analysis and monitoring, users can track their water usage via a web interface, and the system helps in eliminating unfair billing, particularly in shared water meters commonly found in apartment complexes. Arun Gupta [3] the study highlights the high initial costs required for installation and infrastructure, which may limit adoption in resource-constrained regions and points out the importance of having stable internet connectivity, as any disruption could lead to gaps in data transmission and monitoring.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The Smart Wireless Water Meter with Web DB using IoT system integrates advanced sensors, microcontrollers, wireless communication modules, and cloud technologies to monitor and control water usage efficiently. The system consists of two primary components: the transmitter unit, responsible for collecting and transmitting data, and the receiver unit, responsible for receiving and processing the data. This setup ensures real-time monitoring and efficient water management, offering an innovative solution for urban and rural water distribution systems.

A. Transmitter unit:

Fig 1. Block Diagram of Transmitter

The transmitter unit is centred around the ATMEGA328P microcontroller, which plays a crucial role in managing the entire data acquisition process. The microcontroller interfaces with multiple sensors, including water level sensors and water flow sensors, to collect real-time data.

- ATMEGA328P Microcontroller:** This is the central processing unit of the transmitter. It reads the input signals from both the water level sensors and the flow sensor, processes the information, and sends it to the LoRa module. Its efficiency and low power usage make it ideal for such embedded applications.
- Water Level Sensors:** Multiple water level sensors are placed at different heights in the tank (low, medium, high) to monitor the current water status. These sensors detect the presence or absence of water at their positions and send digital signals to the microcontroller. This helps in estimating the volume of water in the tank.
- Water Flow Sensor:** The flow sensor monitors the rate of water flow through the pipeline. It generates pulses proportional to the amount of water passing through. These pulses are counted and translated into flow rate (L/min) or total usage (liters/gallons) by the microcontroller.
- LoRa SX1278 Module:** This module is used for wireless communication between the transmitter and receiver. Once the ATMEGA328P processes sensor data, it sends it wirelessly via LoRa SX1278, which is capable of transmitting over several kilometers with low power consumption.
- Power Supply:** A regulated 5V power source supplies power to all the transmitter components, ensuring smooth and stable operation.

B. Receiver Unit:

Fig 2. Block Diagram of Receiver

At the receiver end, the ESP8266 microcontroller is used to receive the data sent by the LoRa module. The ESP8266 is connected to the internet and is designed to process data from the transmitter unit. Upon receiving the data, the microcontroller stores it in a cloud-based database for remote access. This cloud storage allows users to track water usage in real-time via a web-based dashboard. The ESP8266 also communicates with other peripherals like the relay and the motor, which are essential for controlling water distribution based on the received data.

- ESP8266 Microcontroller (NodeMCU):** This powerful microcontroller comes with built-in Wi-Fi and handles multiple responsibilities like Receiving data from the LoRa SX1278, Analyzing water level and flow information, Uploading this data to cloud platforms like Blynk or ThingSpeak, Controlling relay and motor operation automatically, Sending real-time status to the OLED Display and cloud.
- LoRa SX1278 Module:** This module acts as the receiver of the data sent by the transmitter. It ensures accurate delivery of sensor data to the ESP8266 microcontroller.
- Relay Module:** The relay acts as an electronic switch controlled by the ESP8266. It turns the motor ON or OFF depending on water level conditions or flow readings.
- Motor:** The motor is used to fill the tank with water. When the water level goes below a threshold, the motor is activated via the relay. Once the tank is full, the motor is automatically turned off to prevent overflow.
- OLED Display:** This component provides local visual feedback. It shows important information like current water level, water flow rate, and system alerts. This is useful for users physically present near the receiver unit.
- Cloud Platform (Blynk / ThingSpeak):** This is a web-based IoT platform that stores, visualizes, and analyzes the water data received from the ESP8266. It allows users to monitor the system remotely, view graphs, and receive alerts via mobile or desktop.
- Mobile/Desktop Interface:** The end-user interacts with the system through a smartphone or desktop connected to the internet. They can view water usage, control the motor

manually (if needed), and receive real-time updates or notifications.

- f) **Power Supply:** A stable power source ensures the reliable operation of all components on the receiver side, especially the ESP8266 and peripheral modules.

IV. WORKING

A. Sensor Deployment

The foundation of this smart water monitoring system begins with the deployment of sensors at the transmitter side. Multiple water level sensors are placed at various heights inside a water tank to detect levels like *low*, *medium*, and *full*. These sensors provide real-time status of the water level. In addition, a water flow sensor is integrated into the pipeline to measure the rate at which water is being consumed or supplied. This sensor outputs pulse signals proportional to the water flow, which will later be processed into meaningful units such as liters per minute. Together, these sensors gather all the physical information required for the smart monitoring process.

B. Data Collection (Transmitter side)

The process begins with the ATMEGA328P microcontroller, which acts as the brain of the transmitter unit. It interfaces with two primary sensors: the water flow sensor and water level sensors. The flow sensor detects the rate and total volume of water usage by producing electrical pulses proportional to the water passing through the pipe. Simultaneously, water level sensors, strategically placed inside the water tank, detect whether the tank is empty, half-full, or full by sending digital signals to the microcontroller. Once the microcontroller gathers this data, it processes it into readable form—calculating flow rate in liters or gallons and identifying the tank's current water level status. The processed data is then prepared for transmission.

C. Wireless Transmission (LoRa Communication)

The processed data is sent wirelessly using the LoRa SX1278 module, which is connected to the ATMEGA328P. LoRa, known for its long-range, low-power communication capability, transmits the sensor data from the transmitter unit to the receiver unit even over several kilometers. This makes it ideal for remote agricultural fields, industrial areas, or large housing societies where wired connections are impractical.

D. Data Reception and Processing (Receiver Side)

At the receiver end, another LoRa SX1278 module receives the incoming data and forwards it to the ESP8266 (NodeMCU) microcontroller. The ESP8266 is a Wi-Fi-enabled microcontroller that acts as the central controller on this side. Upon receiving the sensor data, it processes the values to decide whether any action is needed—for example, turning the water pump on or off.

E. Motor Automation and Display

The ESP8266 communicates with a relay module, which functions as an electronic switch. If the water level is detected as low, the ESP8266 triggers the relay to turn on the water pump (motor). When the tank becomes full, the ESP8266 turns the motor off by deactivating the relay. This automation

ensures that the water tank is filled efficiently without manual intervention and prevents overflow. In parallel, the ESP8266 updates an OLED display connected to it. This display shows real-time data including water flow, level status, and motor state. It gives local users immediate visibility of system performance.

F. Cloud Integration and Remote Access

One of the most powerful features of the system is its cloud connectivity. The ESP8266 connects to the internet via Wi-Fi and uploads the sensor data to cloud platforms like Blynk or ThingSpeak. These platforms store and analyze the data, offering users access to graphical representations, consumption history, and custom alerts. Users can then access this data through a mobile or desktop interface. From their smartphone or computer, they can monitor real-time water usage, view alerts such as leaks or excessive usage, and even manually control the motor if needed. This promotes water conservation and user awareness.

V. RESULTS

The Smart Wireless Water Meter system, designed with the integration of various sensors, microcontrollers, and wireless communication modules, provides real-time monitoring and management of water usage. The system was successfully tested to measure water flow and levels, sending this data wirelessly from the transmitter unit (using the ATMEGA328P microcontroller and LoRa SX1278) to the receiver unit (using the ESP8266 microcontroller). The water flow sensor accurately measured water consumption, while the contactless water level sensor monitored the water level in real-time, providing valuable insights into the system's operational efficiency.

The LoRa SX1278 module effectively facilitated long-range wireless communication, enabling the transmission of sensor data over distances of several kilometers. This was particularly important for remote installations, where traditional communication systems are not feasible. The ESP8266 microcontroller on the receiver unit received the transmitted data and displayed the relevant information on the SSD1306 OLED display. Additionally, the system was able to control water flow using the DC water pump, which was activated or deactivated based on the data received from the sensors, ensuring efficient water management.

The system's performance was further validated through tests in various environmental conditions, and the response time for data transmission and pump control was within acceptable limits. The relay control of the motor worked seamlessly, allowing for real-time response to changes in water levels or flow rates. The combination of the water flow and level sensors provided accurate monitoring, and the wireless communication ensured data was transferred without delay, making the system robust and reliable for practical applications.

Overall, the system demonstrated a high level of accuracy in measuring and controlling water usage, providing a reliable solution for remote water management applications. The integration of IoT technologies, including wireless communication via LoRa and cloud-based monitoring with the ESP8266, proved to be an effective approach for creating a smart water management system. This system can

significantly improve water conservation efforts, particularly in areas where water resources are limited or where traditional metering systems are impractical.

VI. CONCLUSION

The Smart Wireless Water Meter with Web Database using IoT provides an effective and modern way to monitor and control water usage automatically. By using water level and flow sensors, the system accurately tracks water consumption and tank status. The transmitter section, powered by the ATMEGA328P, collects this data and sends it wirelessly via the LoRa SX1278 module. On the receiver side, the ESP8266 processes the data, displays real-time information on an OLED screen, controls a motor using a relay, and uploads everything to cloud platforms like Blynk or ThingSpeak. This setup ensures efficient water management with minimal manual effort.

The system promotes smart water usage, reduces wastage, and supports remote monitoring, making it ideal for both homes and farms. Its cost-effectiveness, reliability, and scalability offer great potential for future upgrades like mobile apps or AI-based control. Overall, it's a step forward in using IoT for sustainable resource management.

VII. REFERENCES

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